

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

CHALLENGES AND PECULIARITIES OF INTEGRATION OF INTERNATIONAL MEDIA BRANDS WITH THE GEORGIAN MEDIA SPACE ON THE EXAMPLE OF “FORBES” MAGAZINE

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Abstract

Successful international media outlets try their best to cover as many countries around the world as possible and establish their own local editorial offices. Many of them successfully implement all of this, however, there are often cases when the work of local editorial staff turns out to be unsuccessful. Several media giants have their own editorial offices in Georgia, which are operating successfully.

One of these is the business-analytical magazine “FORBES”. The aim of the article is to analyse the challenges and features of integrating international media brands with the Georgian media space using the example of one of the most influential American magazines in the world, “FORBES”. To determine the functions, history, development trends, specifics, authors, and goals, methods, and forms of its entry into the Georgian media space of a specific international media brand.

Keywords: Media Brands, Transnational Media Corporations, Georgian Media Space, Forbes magazine.

Introduction

A significant part of the planet's population has found itself in a new information reality, which is expressed by the availability of knowledge, news, and information from various areas of life. The audience is given the opportunity to engage in the course of various events in real time. The development of modern technologies and telecommunications networks has eliminated the importance of time and space.

Also, geographical borders were erased, which contributed to the rapprochement of the peoples of the world, their integration into one large global space. International media brands are trying their best to acquire as many countries or regions as possible in order to establish their own editorial offices and thereby grow their audience.

It is very interesting, in general, the main trends in the development of media in the conditions of globalization. Also, how the conceptual models of international media brands are transformed into Georgian reality. It is these issues that determine the relevance of the research topic. The characteristics, principles, and forms and methods of establishing themselves in foreign media space (using the example of Georgia) of famous foreign media brands have not been studied by modern media researchers.

The scientific approaches used in the research to the study of the problem of establishment of the largest and most successful media brands in the foreign media space provide for the study of the wide context of many aspects and aspects of the issue, conceptual analysis. It is particularly important to observe, through the scientific apparatus, the processes of how the conceptual models of international media brands are transformed into Georgian reality, and what specific features and characteristics distinguish this process.

While working on this publication, in order to achieve the main scientific goals, it was necessary to use various qualitative and mixed-method research methods. In total, I used four methods. I believe that the above methods were quite relevant for the in-depth study of the research issue and significantly simplified the provision of answers to the research questions posed in the article. Specifically, these methods are: historical analysis, critical discourse, comparative and content analysis methods.

Using the method of historical analysis, we analysed the important trends in the founding and further development of “FORBES” magazine in the past decades and how it was transformed with the advent of the era of globalization. We used the critical discourse method when analysing various professional scientific literature related to the research topic.

Using the comparative analysis method, we compared the Georgian edition of the international media brand “FORBES” with its original, American version. The method of content analysis helped us to study and characterize both the informative and visual content of the Georgian editions of the business-analytical magazine reviewed in the research.

The use of the approaches and methods presented in the research helped us to present the issue under the study in a diverse and interesting way, so that not only the scientific community, but also anyone interested in the topic in general, could understand and correctly perceive the issues.

Discussion and Results

Some of the content of foreign media outlets turned out to be incompatible with the Georgian media space, which significantly hindered their operation in the media market. Since Georgia gained independence,

a number of foreign news outlets have attempted to establish their own local editorial offices, however, several of them were soon closed.

The examples of success outweigh the failures of international media brands entering and establishing themselves in the Georgian information space. Many publications have managed to satisfy the interest of Georgian readers, gain their loyalty, and they continue to develop steadily on the Georgian media market. One of the clearest examples of this is the business-analytical magazine "FORBES".

Before we talk directly about the Georgian edition of the magazine and the factors that contributed to its success, let's first get acquainted with a brief history of FORBES. "Forbes" magazine was founded on September 15, 1917 in the USA by an American financial journalist of Scottish origin, Bertie Charles Forbes, and still bears the name of its founder.

For more than a century, it has developed into one of the world's most successful, reliable, and authoritative business-analytical print publications, publishing news on the current financial and economic situation both within a country and globally.

Forbes believed deeply in what we would today call entrepreneurial capitalism. The magazine consistently supported and covered any ventures of honest businessmen. The editorial staff often used the slogan - "The bolder, the better." At the same time, the publication harshly criticized those who abused their employees or incompetently managed their companies. In the first issue of Forbes, the editorial board stated: "Business was created to gain happiness, not to accumulate millions" (Forbes, 2017).

The publication experienced a boom in the 1920s. At the time, the famous media magnate William Randolph Hearst offered to buy the magazine in 1928 for a considerable sum, but was immediately rejected by the owner. During the Great Depression, the magazine was on the verge of bankruptcy, having lost almost 80% of its advertising revenue, unlike its main competitor, BusinessWeek. For a period of time, employees were not even paid, but the editorial staff managed to find alternative sources of income and it did not close, unlike several of its relatively small-circulation competitors.

After the years of the Great Depression, the magazine's editorial staff launched a new edition, "The Forbes Investor," which was a weekly newsletter that recommended the purchase of shares of various companies, also analysed the previous week's financial data from various stock exchanges. Also, during the same period, the quality and content of editorial publications improved and refined. Thanks to a number of innovations implemented by the editor-in-chief, the circulation of the publication and advertising revenues increased. Thanks to all this, the magazine surpassed its competitors "Fortune" and "BusinessWeek" in its influence in the business world (Delbridge, 2019).

The website Forbes.com was created in 1996 and currently receives over 27 million unique visitors each month. Forbes.com uses the slogan "The home page for the world's business leaders" and has been one of the most widely visited business websites in the world for

several consecutive years. As of 2019, the company was publishing 100 articles on its online platform daily (Norris, 2021).

Forbes.com uses a kind of contributor network in which freelancers write and publish articles directly on the website. Freelance journalists are paid by the editorial board based on the rating of the material they publish. The more readers an article has, the more the author earns. More than 2,500 freelance journalists currently work with the publication's website, and some of them have already earned more than \$100,000 from their articles, according to the company (Sonderman, 2012).

This globally recognized and successful business-analytical publication has gone through many difficulties on its path to development over the past century. It has undergone complete rebranding several times, and the transformation has directly affected the magazine's content. They were one of the first to embrace digital trends and still maintain a high level of multimedia. Along with all this, the magazine has never deviated from its main principle, which involves the entrepreneurial spirit and helping budding entrepreneurs. The business ratings and writings published in the publication are still considered the most reliable in financial circles, and Forbes remains an objective observer who understands the world's economic pulse.

Today, in addition to "Forbes" magazine itself and its lifestyle supplement, "Forbes Life", the magazine has 42 international editions, covering a total of 69 countries. One of them is Georgia, which joined the big family of "Forbes" in December 2011 and since then it has been published in print monthly. The magazine's initial circulation was 3,000 copies and its price was 10 GEL. Despite the rather substantial cost for that period, the circulation increased significantly in the following years, unlike the price.

Since its establishment, Maya Mirijanashvili has been the permanent publisher of "Forbes Georgia". As for the magazine's editor-in-chief, in the initial period this position was held by Revaz Sakevarishvili. In March 2012, he accused Gagik Eghizarian, founder of Media Partners, the company that owns the rights to Forbes, of interfering with his editorial independence and attempting censorship, after which he resigned. At that time, a special statement by Revaz Sakevarishvili revealed that Eghizarian had always wanted to interfere in the editorial policy and independence of the magazine. However, his last attempt turned out decisive when Eghizarian demanded that a recorded interview with Bidzina Ivanishvili, a well-known businessman who had just entered politics at that time, be shortened (Paradashvili, 2012).

Then, for many years, this position was held by Giorgi Isakadze, who is also the author and host of several business-analytical television programs, including "Business Morning" and "Business Contact". Currently, the editor-in-chief of the magazine is Shota Digmelashvili. The main idea of the Georgian-language publication is fully based on and shares the American one. It involves telling readers about the people, technologies, and ideas that are changing the world.

Like the American edition, the Georgian edition of the magazine is distinguished by its high standards, both in terms of quality and content. One section of the publication is dedicated to economic news in Georgia, and the other to international processes. In addition to economics and finance, the magazine focuses on the latest achievements in the fields of politics, energy, ecology, medicine, technology, education, and transportation.

An important place in the magazine is devoted to the economic processes and news in Georgia. The editorial team's goal is to inform the public about the current situation in the Georgian economy and business. They also told readers stories of successful people who left a great mark on the development of a country or the entire world.

In addition to the main magazine, the editorial board of Georgian "Forbes" also publishes "Forbes Banker", "Forbes Georgia in English" and "Forbes Woman Georgia". The latter is a monthly publication and its goal is to promote the economic empowerment of women in society, introduce readers to the success stories of women in various professions, and prepare analytical articles on topics of high interest.

Like the American edition, the Georgian-language magazine is highly polygraphic and its issues consist of approximately 140 pages. One section of the magazine discusses current business topics from around the world. The second part is entirely devoted to the current financial and economic environment in the country and news about Georgian business. Also, interesting interviews recorded with Georgian entrepreneurs. Thematic columns are distinguished by their consistency and originality. The editor's column is located on the front pages of each issue. In general, among the Georgian authors of the local edition of the magazine, we can single out several well-known figures and businessmen. Also, in every issue of the publication you will find articles written by influential financiers and economists from around the world.

Approximately one-third of the materials in the local Georgian edition are copied from the American magazine. Most often, this category includes columns by foreign authors and news about the world economy. Naturally, the editorial team tries to adapt all American materials published in the magazine to Georgian context. The Georgian edition of the magazine also cooperates with local editorial offices in other countries and interesting materials, research, and publications are exchanged.

On the front cover of each issue of the magazine are printed those famous Georgian or foreign entrepreneurs, whose activities have been evaluated as successful by the Georgian editors of "Forbes". Naturally, it is considered a great honour for each of them to be featured on the cover of such a prestigious magazine, recognized worldwide, as "Forbes". As is clear from the letters received by the editorial office, the original column on the back cover of the magazine, entitled "Opinions", which collects various famous sayings on a specific topic and names their authors, enjoys considerable interest and approval among readers.

Let's describe one case of the Georgian edition of the magazine, for example, the November 2024 issue, which also features 22-year-old Giorgi Shonia on the front cover. He is the founder and director of the technology start up "MONCERO". This Georgian-Swiss company creates user-friendly, highly personalized digital products for large Georgian and foreign companies. One of these products is the crypto platform "NORDOM", which, according to Giorgi, will change the global landscape of the crypto industry. In this issue, readers could read Anina Tefnadze's recorded interview with Giorgi Shonia, entitled "In the Service of Digital Transformation."

In addition to the above-mentioned material, the "Interview and Profile" section presents recorded interviews with several other respondents, including Anina Tefnadze's interview with Georgian producer Albert Zurashvili, titled "A Close-up of Video Masterpieces Producer," journalist Kakhi Chakvetadze's interview with Vepkhia Lominashvili, Head of the Small and Medium Business Department of TBC Bank, titled "Everything for Business," and Iza Gvaramadze's interview with aesthetic medicine specialist Maya Milanova, titled "An Artist in Aesthetic Medicine."

In another section, "Opinion and Facts", the following articles are presented: "The Inevitable Donald Trump" by journalist Aka Zarqua, "Politics as a source of income" by Dan Alexander, and the joint publication of Vakhtang Partsvania and Erekle Pirveli "The Role of Georgia in Avoiding Sanctions: Russia's transit hub?", Beso Namchavadze's "What caused the growth of Georgia's economy in the first half of 2024?" and the article "The Forbes 300" by Gareth Ward, the ambassador of the United Kingdom to Georgia.

The November 2024 issue of the magazine also published "Welcome to Zyn City" by Will Yakovitz, "Mission Impossible" by Monica Hunter-Shart, "Crypto Philosopher's Sovereign" by Javier Paz and Steven Ehrlich, Manit Ahuja and Hank Tucker's "The \$6 Billion Deal," Matt Craig's "Snoop Dogg Bets Big—On Himself," and Anina Tefnadze's "A Time Machine with Marketing Potential," where we are talking about Georgian start-ups, Roman Gujabidze and Gabriel Meliyava, the Printomato device created by them offers users free photos, and brands - a unique advertising opportunity.

The cover of the December 2024 issue features Giorgi Mkheidze, the managing partner of the construction company Metropol. Naturally, readers of the magazine could also read the interview with the aforementioned person recorded by Ananina Tefnadze in the same issue. Two other publications published in the December issue also belong to Anina Tefnadze. The first of which is titled, "Bakuriani 2025: An Olympic Leap into the Digital Future."

In the aforementioned publication, the Chairman of the Organizing Committee of the Olympic Festival, Mamuka Khabareli, and the Head of the IT and Accreditation Department, Zurab Tuskia, answered Forbes Georgia's questions about the festival's preparation period and digital infrastructure. The second article by the same author is titled "The Fire Has Been Lit, the Game

Has Begun," which discusses the positive and negative aspects of electric vehicles.

Traditionally, the editorial column is placed on the front pages of the publication, the title of which in the mentioned issue was: "We want Georgia in Europe and Europe in Georgia!" In the aforementioned publication, Editor-in-Chief Shota Digmelashvili wrote that "Georgia's membership in the European Union is a supra-partisan, national aspiration protected by the country's constitution. Membership of the European Union also means improved opportunities for trade, investment, prosperity and democratic development for us. Stopping this process and distancing ourselves from Western alliances will translate into severe and long-term economic consequences" (Dighmelashvili, 2024).

Featured articles in the December issue include Aka Zarkua's "Syria's Geopolitical Earthquake," Giorgi Tskhadaia's "Escalation in the Russia-Ukraine War: How is Western Policy towards Russia Changing?" as well as the author's report "Kharkov: Fortress of Solitude" by Katya Soldak, Editorial Director of "Forbes" International Editions. As well as Beso Namchavadze's "Trends in the Georgian Construction and Real Estate Sector" and Egnate Shamugia's "National Bank, Foreign Exchange Reserves and Elections."

After the editor's column, in the "Opinion and Facts" section, you will find articles with the following titles: "Which programs does the budget spend the most on?", "Which state-owned companies employ the most people?", "Top 20 largest and most profitable construction and development companies," and "The largest taxpayers." The next column is "Interview and Profile", which presents an interview between Kakhi Chakvetadze and Makuna Tavberidze, Head of Brand Experience and Marketing at TBC Bank, entitled "Education as a Strategic Direction".

In the same column, there are two more interviews. The first is conducted by journalist Iza Gvaramadze with the founder of the National Institute of Endocrinology, Elene Giorgadze. The second one is by Anita Mukaria - with the rector of the Tbilisi Free Academy, Salome Pirveli, entitled "The Road from College to University." The history section contains material prepared by Nika Khoperia about the Egris-Lazika Kingdom.

Based on all of the above, we can say that the December issue of the magazine, which summarizes 2024, was distinguished by diverse and interesting publications, with financial statistics and reliable ratings characteristic of "Forbes".

Along with the printed version of the Georgian-language magazine, the electronic website Forbes.ge is also successfully operating, where, in addition to materials published in previous issues of the publication, there are also such publications, interviews and ratings specially created for the internet website.

The editorial team intends to add television programs, blogs, vlogs, and new formats of Internet broadcasting to the site in the future. The web platform is available in two languages, Georgian and English. In addition to the website, the online version of "Forbes

Georgia" also uses almost all social networks to disseminate information.

Readers are interested in international ratings published in the magazine or on its website. For example, on January 14, 2025, Forbes.ge published an article by Iza Gvaramadze titled "The World's Safest Airlines for 2025," which was based on statistical data from AirlineRatings.com, a website that rates airline safety and services. In the article, Air New Zealand took first place in the list of the 25 safest full-service airlines.

Air New Zealand was slightly behind Qantas, which took the second place in the list. Third place is shared by three airlines – Cathay Pacific, Qatar Airways and Emirates. Among the safest low-cost airlines, Hong Kong Express is leading. In second place is the Australian Jetstar Group, and in third place is Ryanair, founded in Ireland in 1984. The authors of the rating took into account the following indicators to determine the safest airlines in the world: serious incidents in the last two years; fleet age; fleet size; incident rate; fatalities; profitability; IOSA certificate, and others (Gvaramadze, 2025).

The magazine's website also published a ranking of the world's most powerful passports for 2025, based on exclusive data from the International Air Transport Association (IATA) by the Henley Passport Index. The strength of a passport is determined by how many countries its holder can enter without a visa or without prior visa application.

The sole leader in the ranking of the world's most powerful passports this year is Singapore. Singaporean passport holders can travel visa-free to 195 of the world's 227 destinations. Japan is in second place with visa-free travel to 193 destinations. According to the Henley Passport Index, Afghanistan will have the weakest passport by 2025. Over the past year, Afghan citizens have lost their visa-free travel rights to two additional countries. Citizens with an Afghan passport will be able to travel visa-free to only 26 destinations this year. As for Georgia, the country shares 44th place with Moldova in 122 visa-free destinations (Papalashvili, 2025).

Among the rankings published in the printed edition of the magazine or on the online platform, the list of the richest people in the world always arouses great interest among readers. According to data of "Forbes" January 1, 2025 ranking of the richest people, Tesla and SpaceX CEO Elon Musk is still at the top. At the beginning of 2025, Forbes estimated Musk's fortune at \$421.2 billion.

In the second place in the ranking of the richest people is Amazon founder Jeff Bezos, whose fortune is equal to 237 billion US dollars. In the third place is Oracle founder Larry Ellison with 209.7 billion US dollars. Mark Zuckerberg and Bernard Arnault share fourth and fifth place, with \$202.5 billion and \$168.8 billion, respectively. Overall, the wealth of the world's 10 richest people increased from \$1.8 trillion on December 1, 2024, to \$1.9 trillion on January 1, 2025. Seven of them are richer than they were a month earlier (Papalashvili, Forbes: The World's 10 Richest People. January 2025).

In order to support budding entrepreneurs and young leaders, the magazine has always organized various successful competitions. One of them is “30 under 30”. The implementation of this project began in 2018 and is annual. It is still being successfully held. The competition is largely a motivational tool for young people. Because, they can become the owners of the "Forbes" title and attract the attention of the public (Dolidze, 2020).

Georgian Forbes has always paid great attention to the political and social processes taking place within the country. The editorial staff does not shy away from publicly expressing its own opinion and position. One example of this is the statements published by the publication in various years, which described the difficult situation and moods prevailing in the country at that time. Because of this, even the "Forbes Georgia" year-end gala-reception was postponed several times. The magazine took a similar position in the fall of 2024, openly supporting the country's European future.

At the beginning of the appearance of "Forbes" on the Georgian media market, one of its competitors was the local magazine "Kommersant". Which, due to a decrease in circulation in the following years, ceased its print edition and went fully digital. In addition to the news agency, it also has a radio frequency, the recordings of which are also posted on the web platform. Other relatively small-circulation magazines have already failed to compete with the Georgian Forbes; some of them have been closed, while others are still published, albeit with much fewer resources.

Ultimately, we can say that from the publication of the first Georgian issue of Forbes to the present day, the magazine has steadily maintained its readership, while simultaneously adding various periodicals in both Georgian and English. In addition to the main and periodic publications, the magazine is constantly developing its own digital content, a clear example of which is the transformation of the website into a fully modern multimedia product. The materials posted on the Internet platform are promptly distributed on the official pages of various social media of the publication.

Conclusion

Based on the research conducted, we can assume that a certain part of international media brands do not conduct sociological research of the local market before entering the Georgian media space in order to study the audience and create appropriate media content taking into account their mentality and requirements. Accordingly, content that does not fit the mentality of the local reader is doomed to failure.

Unlike the unsuccessful Georgian editorial offices of various international media brands, “Forbes Georgia”, which works in the business-analytics direction, has managed to adapt to the local media space perfectly. It is a Georgian-language licensed edition of "Forbes", which is an American financial magazine and is well known for its rankings of the world's richest people and companies. “Forbes Georgia” covers a wide range of business-related topics, including finance, en-

trepreneurship, technology and politics, as well as medicine and ecology. The magazine also publishes interviews with prominent business leaders in Georgia.

It also analyses current events in the business world. In addition to the printed magazine, the Georgian edition of “Forbes” also has a website, which features news, analysis, and opinions on various business-related topics. The web platform also has a separate section, which features the publication's trusted ratings. Here you will also find publications about the country's leading businesses and business leaders. “Forbes Georgia” is a valuable resource for anyone interested in the Georgian business landscape, providing reliable and timely coverage of the country's business news and trends.

It is part of the global “Forbes” family, one of the world's most trusted sources of business news and analysis. The magazine was first published in Georgia in 2011 and has since become a leading voice in the country's business community. It is considered to be the most successful business analytical publication in Georgia, the interest and circulation of which has not decreased, but is characterized by a growing trend. Georgian Forbes is constantly trying to introduce innovations, a clear example of which is the publication of several supplements to the magazine.

Also, full integration with the digital world, both in terms of the website and social media, as well as television programs. One of the main features of the Georgian-language "Forbes" is its focus on entrepreneurship and innovation. The magazine regularly features successful entrepreneurs in Georgia and pays close attention to new start-ups and innovative businesses.

The editorial office of the publication also organizes events and award ceremonies to celebrate the achievements of the country's leading business leaders and companies. Another important aspect is the coverage of the Georgian economy and its function as a kind of controller. The magazine provides in-depth analysis of key economic indicators such as GDP, inflation, and foreign investment. It also publishes reviews of the government's economic policies and important initiatives. Everyone knows that "Forbes", unlike all its competitors, is also distinguished by the rankings of the country's top companies and business leaders.

The magazine annually publishes a list of the 50 largest companies in Georgia, as well as ratings of the country's best entrepreneurs and businessmen. It is necessary that the local editorial office of an international media brand is constantly in search of innovation. It is important to devote much more space to the coverage of local topics than to translate materials created by editorial offices of other countries and publish them. The creation of informative and meaningful content different from competitors is one of the keys to success, as well as multimedia and adapting to the right target audience in social media.

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